

IMPACT OF GROUP CONFLICT ON EMPLOYEE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract:

In this study, the effects of group conflict are looked at both positively and negatively. Using a multilevel methodology, it examines how task-related conflict affects productivity. The study also looks at how these workers' jobs are done. Both productivity and job satisfaction are affected. Team Challenges were positively correlated with conflict, which was, in turn, a strong predictor of job performance. In accordance with the findings of hierarchical modelling using data from a survey of workers and their supervisors in a private business. Group collaboration Conflict and employee were positively correlated. development obstacles, which had a detrimental impact connected to productivity and job happiness. Furthermore, we found that the workplace mediates the cross-level association between group conflict and individual outcomes like performance and satisfaction. The research's key finding is that workplace disagreement is not always harmful to an organization's ability to succeed. Instead, tension brought on by a conflict at work may make workers feel more accomplished after the task is finished. Similarly, relationship-based stress and conflict frequently have a negative impact on both the person and the organization.

Keywords: Group conflict, job performance, work stress, negative outcomes, sustainable development.

INTRODUCTION:

Although conflict at work is inevitable in teams and organizations, researchers and managers have hardly ever tried to ascertain if conflict is always harmful or whether it might occasionally be beneficial to both individuals and companies. Organizational conflict theorists have mostly focused on its causes and solutions since they generally concur that conflict degrades team and organizational performance. The state of disagreement or miscommunication caused by actual or imagined differences in needs, beliefs, resources, and interpersonal relationships among the organization's members is known as organizational conflict, also known as workplace conflict.

The four basic factors that lead to conflict at work are rivalry, personality differences, conflicting expectations and favoritism, and differences in needs and standards. Companies can reduce workplace tension by preparing for potential confrontations and offering training before problems arise. Similar researches have been conducted by many authors (Benita, 2021; Monica, 2021; Kumar, 2020; Kumar & Shree, 2019; Monica & Supriya, 2019; Mahesh & Uma Rani, 2019; Mahesh, Gigi, & Uma Rani, 2019; Robert & Monisha, 2019; Kumar & Shree, 2018).

Conflict can arise between two people, such as between superiors and subordinates, between department heads, etc. Based on performance, importance to certain groups, and, typically, hostility between unions and management, groups may clash with one another. Interpersonal conflict can also happen in situations of decision difficulty, which are poetically characterized by expressions like "between the devil and the deep blue sea" or "caught on the horns of dilemma."

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Allan Probst (2009) Input, Output, Efficiency, Service Quality, and Outcomes are presented in that sequence as often seen performance metrics. The performance indicators should also be accompanied by explanation data. Quantitative, pertinent, time-bound, quantifiable, and understandable performance indicators are required.

Greer, Jehn, and Mannix (2008) The four conflict aspects are emotions, importance, effectiveness of resolution, and norms. Relationship conflicts are disagreements and incompatibilities among group members over personal issues unrelated to the task at hand, such as worldwide news and social event rumors. Each employee in the banking industry is a member of a role set, which is a group of people who carry out formalized duties and collaborate on related tasks.

Henkin, Cistone, and Dee (2000) Different disputes might have a beneficial or bad effect on a worker's performance. Contrarily, there is no assumption that conflict should be managed. The approach to addressing conflicts in a challenging environment that yields advantageous results, which is crucial for the organization's development. According to preliminary data from the banking industry, there are many disagreements among employees who are still transitioning from one bank to another.

John R. Rizzo, Robert J. House, and Sidney I. Lirtzman (2005) A view-role conflict occurs when a person performs differently than what is expected of them. When one person is subjected to conflicting demands from another, various types of role conflicts develop. For instance, a worker might be pressured to help bank customers at their desk in addition to being asked to participate on a number of time-consuming committees.

Jones, George, and Hill (2000) Reiterate that conflict is an intrinsic part of an organization's life since the goals of diverse stakeholders, such as senior management or executives and personnel, frequently conflict with one another. **Kelly (2012)** Conflict can occasionally result in unpleasant feelings, but it also indicates that both parties are actively participating in the discussion. However, seeing conflicts at work as opportunities to improve operations is a much more successful approach. Undoubtedly, conflict has some glaring disadvantages.

Priyankdesh (2012) Conflict arises between groups as a result of a lack of freedom, authority, and resources. People who value independence frequently oppose the need for interdependence and, to some extent, conformity within a group. Power-seeking individuals compete with one another for status or influence within the organization.

Richard et al (2007) asserts that conflict management improves organizational performance and effectiveness. Effective conflict management refers to the way a business coordinates the activities of individuals and groups to achieve predetermined objectives. **Stack (2005)** figured out that the group's choice will probably be based on newly learned information on the conflict that has probably been obtained.

Zaidi (2012) During his investigation, he found that Bangladesh is the country where employee and employer disputes are the most well-known. Conflicts are related to employee benefits provided by the organization and personnel personality differences. Conflicts should be manageable, but, if they have unfavorable consequences. Top management decisions can cause conflicts to arise in Bangladeshi businesses. Top management and staff typically dispute because there is minimal opportunity for employee input in decision-making.

Conceptual Framework:

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Group conflicts occurs when a misunderstanding arises between the members of the group. Impact on employee performance is to be studied. So, the survey used a standardized questionnaire to depict the impact of group conflict. A sample of 50 employees of an IT organization were drawn on simple random sampling method. The study used closed ended questions with Likert 5-point scale ratings ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. The survey included total of 20 items excluding the demographic factors.

Objective

- To study the impact of group conflict on employee performance.
- To know the effects of group conflicts on employees.
- To study the management of group conflicts in an organization.

Research Design: The descriptive and causal research designs were employed in this study.

Sample Size: The selected features include a sample, which is a technical term. To perform the analysis, we used a sample size of 44 employees from the overall population.

Questionnaire design: The researcher has designed a questionnaire taking Communication, Organizational Politics, Ego Clash, Work Pressure factors as independent variables and Group Conflict as a dependent variable. The questionnaire comprised 24 questions, including 7 demographic questions.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

Table: 1 Demographic Characteristics of the study participants:

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	31	62.0
	Female	19	38.0
	Total	50	100.0
Age	<21	14	28.0
	21-25	18	36.0
	25-30	11	22.0
	>30	7	14.0
	Total	50	100.0
Marital status	Married	22	44.0
	Unmarried	28	66.0
	Total	50	100.0
Years of experience	0-1 years	17	34.0
	1-2 years	17	34.0
	2-3 years	10	20.0
	More than 3 years	6	12.0
	Total	50	100.0
Monthly income	Below 30,000	14	28.0
	30,000-40,000	14	28.0
	40,000- 50,000	16	32.0
	Above 50,000	8	12.0
	Total	50	100.0

Interpretation: Majority of the respondents are Male (62%) and Unmarried (66%). Nearly 36% of age level falls in the level 21-25 years followed by <21 years (28%), 25-30 years (22%) and more than 30 years (14%). Years of experience of the employees are frequently 1-2 years (34%), 1-2 years (34%), 2-3 years and the remaining are more than 3 years (12%). Major income level of the employees is 40,000-50,000 (32%) followed by 30,000-40,000 (28%) and Below 30,000 (28%).

Table 2: tale showing impact from Communication:

Communication				
Sl. No	Statement	N	Mean	Rank
1	During an argument I often say things I regret	50	4.38	1
2	Conflicts arise due to disagreements with others in the group	50	4.28	2
3	When I disagree with someone, I try to communicate with them	50	4.24	3
4	Avoiding discussion of difference with others may reduce the change of conflict	50	4.16	4
5	If I'm angry with someone I try to communicate calmly	50	4.10	5

Interpretation: The mean score and rank are displayed in the table 3. It shows variable “argument” includes highest mean 4.38 followed by Disagreements (4.28), Communication (4.24), Change of conflict (4.16), Calm communication (4.10). All the mean scores are between 4 to 5. It concludes that respondents are agreeing towards all the mentioned factors.

Table 3: table showing impact from Organizational Conflicts

Organizational Conflicts				
Sl. No	Statement	N	Mean	Rank
1	Organisation politics influence the self-interest and performance of an individual	50	4.22	1
2	Organisation politics forces one's own political views among people	50	4.14	2
3	Organisation politics leads to a common decision in a group	50	4.12	3
4	Politics in group level supresses an individual opinion	50	4.06	4

Interpretation: The mean score and rank are displayed in the table 4. It shows variable “self-interest” includes highest mean 4.22 followed by Political views (4.14), Common discussion (4.12), Individual opinion (4.06). All the mean scores are between 4 to 5. It concludes that respondents are agreeing towards all the mentioned factors.

Table 4: Table showing impact of Ego Clash

Ego Clash				
S.No	Statements	N	Mean	Rank
1	Ego driven behaviour demotivates an individual to open up in a group	50	4.30	1
2	Ego clash within a group may lead to avoiding interaction with the employees	50	4.20	2
3	Ego is one of the biggest barriers to people working in a group	50	4.06	3
4	Ego clash between the employee destroys their effectiveness	50	3.98	4

Interpretation: The mean score and rank are displayed in the table 5. It shows variable “Demotivation” includes highest mean 4.30 followed by Avoidance (4.20), Biggest barriers (4.06), Effectiveness (3.98). All the mean scores are between 3 to 5. It concludes that respondents are agreeing towards all the mentioned factors.

Table: 5: table showing impact of Work Pressure

Work pressure				
Sl. No		N	Mean	Rank
1	The intergroup conflicts increase the burden of work and cause strain	50	4.16	1
2	During conflicts job responsibilities are not clearly defined for an individual	50	4.16	2
3	Conflicts in group cause stress for an individual due to lack of social support	50	4.16	3
4	Healthy relationship at group level reduces the work stress for an individual	50	4.04	4

Interpretation: The mean score and rank are displayed in the table 6. It shows variable “Burden” includes highest mean 4.16 followed by Job responsibilities (4.16), Social support (4.16), Healthy relationship (4.04). All the mean scores are between 4 to 5. It concludes that respondents are agreeing towards all the mentioned factors.

Conclusion:

It happens frequently in society to have disagreements. It is a component of all social systems and acts as a mechanism and process for establishing relationships between people. The capacity to manage relationships is necessary for conflict resolution. Humans and communities both fall short of ideal, conflict-free perfection. Conflict, disagreement, and antagonism are constant and inevitable parts of societal development. Every firm experiences conflict as a result, and how well it is handled affects employee productivity and, ultimately, organizational results. Conflict management is more challenging in developing countries when productivity is rising. According to the report, few people in the nation are aware of the fighting there. The respondents' responses were the same as any other person may have given.

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